

Online Learning Techniques for Occupancy Detection on Resource Constrained Devices

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Abstract—In light of the increasing impact of climate change, the demand for energy-efficient solutions across various sectors is becoming crucial. This paper explores the feasibility of utilizing Online Learning techniques to detect room occupancy in smart buildings, addressing the challenges of privacy and cost. Our methodology leverages existing environmental sensor data without requiring additional hardware, ensuring privacy and cost efficiency. The adaptability of Online Learning models to new environments is a key advantage, eliminating the need for extensive data storage and making the approach suitable for real-world applications. This research focuses on developing and testing this innovative approach, emphasising the constraints of embedded devices to ensure practical deployment without new hardware requirements. Our extensive testing campaign evaluates the performance of the five most commonly used algorithms in this field, highlighting the viability of Online Learning techniques for deployment on embedded devices. This research lays the foundation for developing energy-efficient solutions in smart buildings, offering a cost-effective and privacy-oriented approach to occupancy detection.

Index Terms—Occupancy Detection, IoT, HVAC Systems, Embedded Devices, Online Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems in buildings are responsible for over 38% of building energy use worldwide, reaching more than 60% in the European Union [1]. Alarmingly, this figure is projected to increase due to growing urbanization, rising living standards, and the expanding demand for indoor climate control. Traditionally, HVAC systems operate at full capacity regardless of actual occupancy, leading to significant energy wastage. This issue is anticipated to be exacerbated by the rise of hybrid work models post-COVID-19, further increasing unnecessary energy use. In this context, systems that integrate occupancy detection in the HVAC controller can reduce energy consumption from 29% to 80% [2].

This work emphasizes the importance of developing non-intrusive, cost-effective occupancy detection methods that do not compromise privacy or necessitate extensive retrofitting. It explores leveraging existing building infrastructure, such as

data from temperature, humidity, and CO₂ sensors, to detect occupancy using the adaptability of Online Learning models. This strategy offers precise occupancy detection without the limitations of traditional sensor-based systems, which often rely on specialized sensors or costly computational hardware, or use cameras that raise privacy concerns.

In the investigation of the problem of Occupancy detection, this work starts with the following research question: *How can we develop a methodology for occupancy detection that is accurate, cost-effective, and privacy-oriented?* Specifically, the work aims to address the following specific questions:

- Q1:** How can we adapt machine learning models to new environments without the need for extensive data storage?
- Q2:** What are the performance implications of using Online Learning techniques for occupancy detection in real-world IoT settings, particularly concerning embedded device constraints?

In more detail, the main contributions of this work are:

- A novel methodology for occupancy detection that leverages Online Learning techniques to adapt to new environments without extensive data storage;
- A technique to solve the problem of occupancy detection directly on the edge devices;
- A detailed comparison of Online Learning models for occupancy detection, evaluating their performance in real-world IoT settings (i.e. answering Q1); and
- An analysis of the performance implications of using Online Learning techniques for occupancy detection in embedded device settings, considering memory and computational constraints (i.e. answering Q2).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the key concepts from the literature that underpin this research. Section III outlines the proposed approach, detailing the methodology and techniques used for occupancy detection. Section IV describes the experimental setup, including the datasets used and the models tested. Section V presents the test results, comparing the performance

of the models and analyzing their implications for embedded devices. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper, summarizing the key findings and outlining future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

This section introduces the key concepts from the literature that underpin this research. Particular attention is given to related work in the field of embedded machine learning. Following this, the chapter presents the most significant techniques used to address the occupancy detection problem, highlighting the common issues these methods share.

A. Machine Learning and Online Learning

Machine Learning (ML) [3] allows computers to learn from data without explicit programming, with the primary goal of developing algorithms for data prediction. ML algorithms are categorized into three types [4]: supervised learning (expert-labeled data), unsupervised learning (pattern recognition), and reinforcement learning (learning from environment interactions to maximize rewards). This work focuses on supervised learning, particularly decision trees [5] and deep learning neural networks [6]. Decision trees classify data using a hierarchical structure of features, while deep learning networks automatically extract and learn features through layered structures, eliminating manual intervention.

Online Learning (OL) [7], [8], a branch of ML, focuses on learning from continuous data streams, making it suitable for real-time applications. This work employs OL algorithms to adapt models for accurate occupancy detection in smart buildings. Key algorithms include Hoeffding Trees [9], which use the Hoeffding bound for node splitting without storing data batches, and Hoeffding Adaptive Trees (HAT) [10], which use ADWIN (Adaptive Windowing) [11] to detect concept drift and prune the tree accordingly. Additionally, the Adaptive Random Forest (ARF) [12], an ensemble of Hoeffding Trees with random feature selection, enhances model generalization and adaptability to new data streams.

B. Embedded Machine Learning

In the last few years, the interest in deploying ML models on embedded devices has grown exponentially. The main reason is the need to have a model that can work in real time without the need to send the data to a central server. The main challenge in this field is the limited computational power and memory available on these devices. Really important in this field is the TinyML foundation¹ that is responsible for the most used library for deploying ML models on microcontrollers, i.e. TensorFlow Lite for Microcontrollers². While the topic of ML at the edge is in the developing phase, the field of training ML models on microcontrollers is still in its infancy. The challenge that derives from the world of embedded devices joins the one of online learning, where the model has to adapt to the new data without the need to store them. An important work in this field is the one from Ren et

al. [13] that edited the TinyML library to enable the continuous training of part of the model on the microcontroller itself.

C. Machine Learning Techniques for Occupancy Detection

Given the issue's significance, various approaches are documented in the literature. These approaches primarily fall into two categories: the **Image Based approach**, which employs cameras to detect people's presence in a room, and the **Data Based approach**, which utilizes sensor data from the room to achieve the same goal. Considering the privacy and the cost, the second approach is the one that is more suitable for our context. In the literature, we can find a lot of different approaches to tackle this problem. An interesting proposal comes from Wilhelm, Jakob, and Ahrens [14] that, focusing on the CO₂ concentration, propose a technique called *Motif clustering* using the *STOMP algorithm* to extract distinct occupancy patterns from the CO₂ data.

Another study on the CO₂ concentration for occupancy detection was made by Giardini [15]. Data was collected and sent to a central server via MQTT, where a machine learning model analyzed CO₂ levels, their change over time, and deviations from a baseline, incorporating time to account for daily patterns. A "Two Step Estimate" method first predicted window states. Then, it is used to forecast occupancy, employing Linear Regression and Decision Trees, enhanced with regularization and the Random Forest algorithm to reduce overfitting. Conducted in two offices, the models achieved more than 97% accuracy, but when testing a unified model for both rooms indicated a performance dip. This highlights the challenges in generalizing across different spaces.

Really interesting work was done by Candanedo and Feldheim [16] that, also using temperature and humidity data, tested four different algorithms, evaluating each of them on different input features. The algorithms chosen are Linear Discriminant Analysis [17], Gradient Boosting Machine [18], CART [19], and Random Forest [20]. As the authors state, the most interesting result comes from the CART because it can achieve really high accuracy, keeping the explainability typical of a decision tree.

Madeira and Nunes [21] explored occupancy detection using user interactions with IoT devices in houses, leveraging a platform called Muzzley to collect data from various devices. They decided to test with three different algorithms: SelectKBest [22], LinearSVC [23], and Random Forest [20]. Initial results showed near-perfect accuracy but were skewed due to data imbalance. A refined approach, focusing on users with sufficient daily interactions, achieved around 80% accuracy, suggesting this method's potential as an additional feature in sensor-based models.

III. PROPOSED APPROACH

As discussed in the Introduction, accurately detecting room occupancy plays a vital role in the management of building systems. Occupancy detection in offices comes with an additional set of challenges that we need to face to achieve our goal. At first, we have to ensure the occupants' privacy,

¹<https://www.tinyml.org/>

²<https://www.tensorflow.org/lite/microcontrollers>

Fig. 1. Diagram of the proposed methodology.

excluding every type of sensor that can hear or see what is happening in the room. Then, to create a solution that can actually be applied in the real world, we need to consider the cost. The solution is designed not to require any additional hardware besides the one already installed in HVAC systems, like temperature, humidity, and CO₂ sensors.

A. Architecture

To solve the problem of occupancy detection, with all the challenges and constraints presented in the previous sections, this research presents an innovative approach testing various techniques for online learning since they are ideal for adapting to data variations while maintaining high accuracy. Following the diagram in Figure 1, the model is initially trained on a different dataset composed of real-world data coming from a Siemens building, using batch learning to establish a solid baseline. Upon real-world deployment, it shifts to continuous learning, refining its knowledge based on environmental sensor data specific to the new room.

Specifically, in order to create the general model, all the data available are preprocessed to remove noise and trends. After that, the feature vector shown in 1 is created.

$$[Temp, Hum, CO_2, Temp_d, Hum_d, CO_{2d}, Min_of_the_day, Day_of_the_week] \quad (1)$$

The feature vector includes the following elements: **Temp** represents the current temperature in degrees Celsius, which gives an idea of the indoor environment conditions. **Hum** stands for the current humidity level, expressed as a percentage. **CO₂** is the concentration of carbon dioxide in the air, measured in ppm. The next three features, **Temp_d**, **Hum_d**, and **CO_{2d}**, capture the temperature, humidity, and CO₂ derivatives, respectively. Lastly, **Min_of_the_day** represents the minute of the day, and **Day_of_the_week** is an integer that encodes the current day, where 0 corresponds to Monday and 6 to Sunday.

The last step is to balance the dataset using a simple undersampling technique, which involves reducing the number of samples from the majority class to match the minority class,

which helps prevent the model from being biased towards the more frequent class. After balancing the dataset, we proceed to train the general model, ensuring that it can effectively learn from balanced data and perform well across different occupancy scenarios.

After creating the general model, the model is deployed in the real world. To effectively adapt the model in an online learning scenario without storing all data, it is crucial to preprocess data by filtering out noise using a sliding window and removing trends and seasonality. This is done using the same techniques described before for the general model, using the averages as a baseline to adjust for sensor drift and seasonal effects. The class-balancing algorithm must adapt to real-world deployment by balancing the dataset without storing all the data. The chosen implementation uses online undersampling to maintain class balance by setting a threshold for the sample count difference between majority and minority classes. Excess majority class samples are discarded as new data arrives. Additionally, boosting the weights of new, especially minority, samples enhances learning by prioritizing their impact, improving model adaptability and responsiveness to data shifts.

At this point, data are still not labelled, so to use them to update the model, two strategies to label them are proposed:

- **Temporary External Sensor Integration:** An external sensor, such as a passive infrared detector, detects human presence to label occupancy data, enabling the model to learn occupancy patterns over a few weeks. After this phase, the sensor can be removed or relocated to optimize its use.
- **Leveraging User Interactions:** The system uses interactions with room devices like thermostats or light switches as occupancy indicators, enabling data labelling without extra hardware. This cost-effective method keeps the model updated with current room usage patterns.

Our solution combines both strategies, initially using an external sensor for clear occupancy signals and then transitioning to user interaction data. This approach quickly adapts the model to occupancy patterns and continuously refines it for sustained accuracy, accommodating evolving room usage over time.

B. Models

The selection of appropriate online learning models for occupancy detection complements the architectural design of the proposed methodology. Different models were tested to evaluate their performance, focusing not only on accuracy but also on resource consumption, particularly memory and computational power. To do that, each model underwent a session of tests to evaluate the Geometric Mean Score with a holdout set, and then the throughput and the memory footprint were measured on a Raspberry Pi 4B. The models tested are the Hoeffding Tree with its adaptive version, the Adaptive Random Forest, and the TinyOL [13].

To conduct a comprehensive assessment, each model underwent rigorous testing to evaluate its Geometric Mean Score

using a holdout set. This step demonstrates the potential of the adaptation mechanism, comparing it with traditional machine learning techniques. The models were further evaluated for their resource efficiency after this accuracy assessment. Key metrics such as throughput and memory footprint were measured on a Raspberry Pi 4B, a widely used embedded device, to ensure the feasibility of deploying these models in real-world scenarios without requiring significant hardware upgrades.

The models tested include the Hoeffding Tree and its adaptive version, which is known for robust performance and minimal resource consumption. The Adaptive Random Forest was evaluated for handling complex data patterns with improved accuracy. Lastly, TinyOL [13], a neural network-based model, was tested for using neural networks in resource-constrained environments.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this chapter, we describe the experimental setup used to evaluate the proposed methodology for occupancy detection. We outline the research hypotheses, datasets, models tested, deployment strategy, and metrics used to assess the performance and feasibility of our approach. This comprehensive setup ensures that our results are both reliable and applicable to real-world scenarios.

A. Research Hypotheses

We formulated the following hypotheses to guide our research:

- H1:** Online Learning models will outperform traditional machine learning models in occupancy detection, demonstrating superior accuracy and adaptability.
- H2:** The use of Online Learning models is feasible for deployment on embedded devices, offering a balance between performance and resource efficiency.

B. Datasets

We worked mainly with two datasets to experiment with and create the proposed methodology. The first one is composed of data collected by Siemens³ in one of its buildings, which has 63 rooms and two years of data. The second one comes from a device developed as a test platform. It is based on a Raspberry Pi Zero W using the SCD41 sensor to collect the temperature, humidity, and CO₂ in four conference rooms of another Siemens office.

As illustrated in Figure 2, our evaluation methodology begins by analyzing and preprocessing the Siemens dataset. Subsequently, the model is trained using the first 70% of the data, while the remaining 30% is reserved as a holdout set for testing purposes. This temporal split ensures that the test set strictly consists of the most recent 30% of the samples, thereby preventing data leakage and providing a realistic assessment of model performance. The deployment of the

³The Siemens building dataset used in this study is internal and not publicly accessible. It contains two years of room-level data, including temperature, CO₂, humidity, and occupancy status (vacant or occupied).

Fig. 2. Experimental Setup.

model is then simulated using the data collected from our offices. All the processes simulate real-world deployment, so data are preprocessed as a stream and the model is updated in real-time.

C. Tested Models

A total of six online learning models were tested and compared to one using a traditional machine learning approach.

- **CART:** One of the most common proposed approaches in the literature. It is tested with a simple tree using the Gini index as the split criterion, with a max depth of 15.
- **HT:** Hoeffding tree classifier using the information gain as the split criterion and max depth 15.
- **HAT:** Hoeffding Adaptive Tree classifier using ADWIN as a drift detector, information gain as the split criterion, and max depth 15.
- **ARF10:** Adaptive Random Forest with 10 trees and depth 15.
- **ARF50:** Adaptive Random Forest with 50 trees and depth 15.
- **Small TinyOL:** Dense Neural Network composed of three hidden layers of 64, 64, and 32 neurons with ReLU activation function and a total of 6866 parameters using only the last two layers for adaptation.
- **Big TinyOL:** Dense Neural Network composed of four hidden layers of 64, 128, 64, and 32 neurons with ReLU activation function and a total of 19282 parameters using only the last two layers for adaptation.

These models are tested using Python with mainly three libraries: Scikit-learn⁴, TensorFlow⁵, and River⁶.

D. Deployment

To assess deployment feasibility, we tested each model on a Raspberry Pi 4B⁷, featuring a Quad-core Cortex-A72 64-bit processor and 4 GB of RAM. While more powerful than the intended final target, this platform is accessible for initial testing. The goal is to deploy the solution on a microcontroller, such as the STM32F7 series⁸, which offers up to 2MB of flash memory and 512KB of RAM. Microcontrollers provide

⁴<https://scikit-learn.org/>

⁵<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

⁶<https://riverml.xyz/>

⁷<https://www.raspberrypi.com/products/raspberry-pi-4-model-b/>

⁸<https://www.st.com/en/microcontrollers-microprocessors/stm32f7-series.html>

affordability, energy efficiency, and compactness, enabling real-time on-device processing, reducing costs, and enhancing data privacy.

E. Metrics

Evaluating our methodology requires selecting metrics that accurately reflect performance, especially given the unique challenges posed by our dataset and deployment goals. Our analysis focuses on both the accuracy of occupancy detection in imbalanced datasets and the feasibility of deploying the solution on resource-constrained devices.

For imbalanced datasets, such as the Siemens dataset with a 1:10 positive to negative class ratio, traditional accuracy is not reliable because it tends to favor the majority class, potentially leading to misleadingly high performance. To mitigate this issue, we use the Geometric Mean Score, which accounts for both sensitivity and specificity, providing a more balanced evaluation of model performance in imbalanced scenarios.

To evaluate the feasibility and scalability of our solution, we also measured memory consumption and throughput on the Raspberry Pi during both inference and training. High throughput is essential to ensure that the solution can be scaled down to a microcontroller, which has more limited resources. Throughput was assessed by processing over 20,000 samples, ensuring that the calculated average reflected any initialization operations. This measurement, expressed in samples per second, helps us gauge the system's capability to perform in real time under resource constraints.

V. TEST RESULTS

This section begins with an analysis of the accuracy performance of the various models and concludes with an examination of their resource requirements, which is crucial for the embedded devices that are the focus of this work.

Figure 3 shows the geometric mean scores for all tested models, clearly illustrating the superior performance of adaptive models over non-adaptive ones. The widely-used CART model, despite its prevalence, scores significantly lower than the adaptive models, emphasizing the critical role of adaptability, as confirmed by H1. Among the adaptive models, performance differences are minimal, with the Adaptive Random Forest model achieving the highest score, outperforming the HAT model by 2-4 percentage points. Other adaptive models also perform well, further underscoring the value of adaptability in dynamic environments. This analysis confirms that adaptability is essential for maintaining high performance, as reflected in the consistently strong results of the adaptive models.

Considering the constraints of embedded devices, further analysis is necessary to understand the impact of the model on the memory and computational power of these devices. To achieve this, we conducted tests on a Raspberry Pi 4, comparing the throughput during both inference and training phases. This detailed comparison aims to identify the most efficient models for deployment in IoT environments where resources are limited. The testing methodology measured the

time required to process the entire test set. By doing so, we obtained average results that mitigate the influence of sporadic system delays, ensuring a more accurate assessment of each model's performance.

The results of these tests on the models that can be continuously adapted are presented in Figure 4. One key observation is that the ARF50 model is too large to be tested on the Raspberry Pi 4, which led to its exclusion from the graph. This limitation highlights the importance of considering model size when selecting algorithms for embedded systems. In analyzing the graph, we notice a significant difference in performance between the HT and HAT models compared to other tested models. The superior throughput of HT and HAT indicates their efficiency, making them optimal candidates for deployment on IoT devices. This performance advantage is critical, as it translates to faster processing times, leaving more resources available for other tasks. Moreover, the results underscore the necessity of balancing model complexity with the hardware capabilities of embedded devices. While more complex models might offer improved accuracy, their resource demands can render them impractical for use in constrained environments. Therefore, selecting models like HT and HAT, which offer a good trade-off between performance and resource usage, is essential for successfully deploying machine learning solutions in IoT applications. Furthermore, the high throughput achieved in our experiments suggests that even less powerful and lower-cost devices could be used effectively. This means that our solution can be deployed on simpler, more affordable embedded devices without compromising performance, making the approach more cost-effective and scalable for widespread adoption in smart buildings. Another important aspect to consider is the memory footprint of the model. In Figure 5, we present the memory usage of the tested models. It is clear that the ARF models are too large for practical use in this type of application using around 9550KB of RAM, almost 70 times the HT. Interestingly, the neural network (NN) models have the smallest memory footprints, just 28KB and 78KB for the small and the big model tested respectively. However, it is important to note that with NNs, we must also consider the memory required to store the library used to run the model and the memory needed to temporarily store the layer weights during computation. Taking all these factors into account, HT and HAT models seem to offer a good trade-off between memory usage, execution time, and performance, making them suitable for deployment in embedded systems, confirming H2.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study presents a novel methodology for occupancy detection in smart buildings, utilizing Online Learning techniques to adapt to real-world data and achieve high accuracy. Our approach effectively addresses critical challenges such as privacy, cost, and resource constraints, providing a practical and scalable solution for energy-efficient building management.

Fig. 3. Comparison of model performance (transposed)

Fig. 4. Comparison of models throughput

Fig. 5. Comparison of model memory footprint

In terms of privacy, the solution leverages non-intrusive environmental sensors (temperature, humidity, CO₂) that do not collect personally identifiable information, ensuring that sensitive data about occupants are not gathered. Moreover, the entire processing of sensor data is done locally on the device, eliminating the need for cloud-based data transfer or storage. By keeping all computations on edge devices, such as microcontrollers or the Raspberry Pi used in our tests, we significantly reduce the risk of data breaches and privacy violations, as no personal or behavioral data leaves the local environment.

From a cost-efficiency standpoint, our solution is designed to minimize additional hardware investments by leveraging existing infrastructure, including environmental sensors commonly integrated into HVAC systems. In typical office buildings, centralized HVAC systems are equipped with devices in each room that function as thermostats. Our solution is specifically tailored to enhance these devices by introducing new capabilities without requiring any hardware replacement, ensuring a seamless and cost-effective deployment. The use of low-cost microcontrollers for real-time, on-device processing further reduces operational costs by eliminating the need for external servers or cloud infrastructure, which typically involve ongoing costs for data transmission, storage, and cloud services. Additionally, our approach reduces energy consumption since the models are optimized for efficient, low-power devices such as microcontrollers, making the system highly cost-effective for large-scale deployment in smart buildings. By processing data locally and removing the need for cloud communication, we both enhance privacy protections and significantly reduce costs.

Experiments conducted on Raspberry Pi 4 demonstrate the efficacy of our methodology, highlighting the superior performance of adaptive models in dynamic environments, confirming H1 and answering Q1. By maintaining a standardized scenario, we ensured the comparability of results across different techniques. The findings underscore the importance of adaptability in maintaining high accuracy and performance, particularly in scenarios with changing data distributions.

Additionally, our analysis of model throughput and memory usage on Raspberry Pi 4 provides valuable insights into the practical deployment of machine learning solutions in Internet of Things applications, confirming H2 and answering Q2. Understanding how different models perform under the constraints of limited computational resources and memory capacity is crucial for effective implementation.

Our results identify HT and HAT models as optimal choices for deployment in these environments. These models balance performance, resource usage, and efficiency, exhibiting low memory footprints and high throughput. This makes them well-suited for real-time applications where computational resources are limited.

In summary, the proposed methodology enhances occupancy detection accuracy and ensures efficient use of resources, paving the way for smarter, more energy-efficient buildings.

In future work, we plan to extend our exploration of embedded online learning by addressing key limitations from this study. First, we will incorporate larger and more diverse datasets to capture long-term patterns and seasonal variations, improving the generalizability of the model. We also aim to integrate the occupancy detection system with existing HVAC control systems to optimize energy consumption, demonstrating its real-world impact on energy efficiency. Additionally, we will focus on optimizing memory usage and execution time for deployment on resource-constrained devices, using techniques like model pruning and quantization. These steps will enhance the feasibility of using the solution in low-power, low-memory environments, expanding its applicability in real-world smart building applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. González-Torres, L. Pérez-Lombard, J. F. Coronel, I. R. Maestre, and D. Yan, "A review on buildings energy information: Trends, end-uses, fuels and drivers," *Energy Reports*, vol. 8, pp. 626–637, Nov. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S235248472101427X>
- [2] J. Brooks, S. Kumar, S. Goyal, R. Subramany, and P. Barooah, "Energy-efficient control of under-actuated HVAC zones in commercial buildings," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 93, pp. 160–168, Apr. 2015.
- [3] R. J. Solomonoff, "A formal theory of inductive inference. Part II," *Information and Control*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 224–254, Jun. 1964.
- [4] S. Sah, "Machine Learning: A Review of Learning Types," Jul. 2020.
- [5] J. R. Quinlan, "Induction of decision trees," *Machine Learning*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 81–106, Mar. 1986.
- [6] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, "Deep learning," *Nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436–444, May 2015.
- [7] A. Bifet, R. Gavaldà, G. Holmes, and B. Pfahringer, *Machine Learning for Data Streams with Practical Examples in MOA*. MIT Press, 2018.
- [8] S. C. H. Hoi, D. Sahoo, J. Lu, and P. Zhao, "Online Learning: A Comprehensive Survey," Oct. 2018.
- [9] P. Domingos and G. Hulten, "Mining high-speed data streams," in *Proceedings of the Sixth ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, ser. KDD '00. New York, NY, USA: Association for Computing Machinery, Aug. 2000, pp. 71–80.
- [10] A. Bifet and R. Gavaldà, "Adaptive Learning from Evolving Data Streams," Aug. 2009, pp. 249–260.
- [11] —, "Learning from Time-Changing Data with Adaptive Windowing," in *Proceedings of the 7th SIAM International Conference on Data Mining*, vol. 7, Apr. 2007.
- [12] H. M. Gomes, A. Bifet, J. Read, J. P. Barddal, F. Enembreck, B. Pfahringer, G. Holmes, and T. Abdessalem, "Adaptive random forests for evolving data stream classification," *Machine Learning*, vol. 106, pp. 1–27, Oct. 2017.
- [13] H. Ren, D. Anicic, and T. Runkler, "TinyOL: TinyML with Online-Learning on Microcontrollers," Apr. 2021.
- [14] S. Wilhelm, D. Jakob, and D. Ahrens, "Human Presence Detection by monitoring the indoor CO₂ concentration," Sep. 2020.
- [15] M. Cesana, A. Redondi, and E. Longo, "Machine learning methods for indoor occupancy detection with CO₂ multi-sensor data," 2018.
- [16] L. M. Candanedo and V. Feldheim, "Accurate occupancy detection of an office room from light, temperature, humidity and CO₂ measurements using statistical learning models," *Energy and Buildings*, vol. 112, pp. 28–39, Jan. 2016.
- [17] S. Mika, G. Ratsch, J. Weston, B. Scholkopf, and K. Mullers, "Fisher discriminant analysis with kernels," in *Neural Networks for Signal Processing IX: Proceedings of the 1999 IEEE Signal Processing Society Workshop (Cat. No.98TH8468)*. Madison, WI, USA: IEEE, 1999, pp. 41–48.
- [18] J. Friedman, "Greedy Function Approximation: A Gradient Boosting Machine," *The Annals of Statistics*, vol. 29, Nov. 2000.
- [19] R. Lewis, "An Introduction to Classification and Regression Tree (CART) Analysis," Jan. 2000.

- [20] L. Breiman, "Random Forests," *Machine Learning*, vol. 45, no. 1, pp. 5–32, Oct. 2001.
- [21] R. Madeira and L. Nunes, "A machine learning approach for indirect human presence detection using IOT devices," in *2016 Eleventh International Conference on Digital Information Management (ICDIM)*, Sep. 2016, pp. 145–150.
- [22] L. Ladicky and P. Torr, "Linear Support Vector Machines," pp. 985–992, Jan. 2011.
- [23] J. Tsotsos, I. Kotseruba, A. Andreopoulos, and Y. Wu, *A Possible Reason for Why Data-Driven Beats Theory-Driven Computer Vision*, Aug. 2019.